

Influence of Thirumanimutharu river water on soil properties of Veerapandi Block villages of Salem district

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Abstract : A detailed soil survey was conducted to estimate Thirumanimutharu river basin of Salem district Veerapandi block that is polluted by effluent discharge. The soil analytical results of villages revealed that the soil is tending towards alkalinity both in surface and subsurface. However, the accumulation of soluble salts (EC) in the soil is quite normal. Accounting for 96 per cent of the area, since the physical condition of the most soil series favours the natural way of leaching out the salts, which require adequate measures for their reclamation. The occurrence of saline alkaline lands is quite negligible.

Keywords : Saline, alkaline, pH, EC.

Introduction

The undesirable change in soil due to pollution affects the physiological processes that inhibit the plant growth, photosynthesis and reduce the productivity as well as quality of the agricultural produce. The pollution of soil differs from air and water pollution in that the pollutants remain in direct or close contact with soil environment for relatively longer period and affect plant growth. Soil pollution sources of urban wastes, agricultural practices, biological agents and industrial wastes; mind is supposed to be the original and basic pollutant responsible for pollution hazards and their toxic effects consequently in soil either surface or subsurface or both. Among all the sources of pollution, however, clusters of industrial establishments located in and around Salem play a key role in the degradation of the Thirumanimutharu basin. Many of the industrial effluents are discharged either as such or without adequate treatment into streams that drain into Thirumanimutharu or dumped into the surrounding lands.

Experimental

A detailed soil survey was conducted to estimate Thirumanimutharu river basin of Salem district Veerapandi block that is polluted by effluent discharge. For that profile studies, surface and subsurface soil samples were collected in 13 villages, analysed in the soil testing labora-

tory for its pH¹, Electrical Conductivity (EC), soil organic carbon (OC)², available N, P, K and micronutrients³.

Results and discussion

The soil analytical results of villages like Papparapatty, Veerapandi, Akkarapalayam, Agraharapulaveri and Uthamasolapuram revealed that the soil are tending towards alkalinity both in surface and subsurface. Thirumanimutharu basin are non alkaline in soil reaction, genetically, but, upon soil pollution, these soil have been rendered alkaline at present and significant increase both in soil reaction (pH) and soluble salts content (EC) were noticed.

Soil series :

Detailed information on the nature, extent and distribution of different soils occurring in the Thirumanimutharu river water affected area of Veerapandi block. During the course of survey 17 soil series with 22 phases were identified. In general all soil series are affected by river water pollution except Puthur Agraharam and Pudurmalayampatty series all the 15 soil series soil profile surface and subsurface soils having the pH range of 8.3–8.8 and subsurface soil pH ranges from 8.3–9.0 sub soil series are more affected by the Thirumanimutharu river

pollution water. The soil has become degraded over a period of time after the industrial revolution on account of the accumulation of Thirumanimutharu wastes dominated with the industrial effluents. Soil reaction (pH) and concentration of soluble salts (EC) are found to be increased by and large in the soils close to the sources of contamination. Salinity is seen to the small extent in the surface and in the subsurface. The intensity of salinity or saline alkaline condition is comparatively less than that of the alkalinity. These soils require adequate measures of reclamation including chemical amendments for supporting crop plants. Saline soils require adequate leaching of

accumulated salts by using good water⁴.

Surface and subsurface soil :

Most of the soil series occurring in the Thirumanimutharu basin are non-alkaline in soil reaction, genetically, but, upon soil pollution, these soils have been rendered alkaline at present. The soil analytical results of villages like Papparapatty, Virapandi, Akkarapalayam, Agraharapulaveri and Uthamasolapuram revealed that the soils are tending towards alkalinity both in surface and subsurface soils. The village-wise soil analytical data of Thirumanimutharu river basin presented in the Table 1 is suggestive of significant increase both in soil reaction

Table 1. Analytical details of Thirumanimutharu river basin of Salem district of Veerapandi block

Sr. no.	Village name	Soil series	pH-S	pH-SS	EC-S	EC-SS	Texture-S	LS-S	CEC	ESP	OC
1.	Muttanampalayam	Perumampatti	7.75	7.9	0.25	0.2	Scl	Ca	38.5	7.6	0.26
2.	Velanatham	Kurakkapuram	7.95	7.85	1	1.2	Scl	Ca	25.3	16.6	0.6
3.	Papparapatty	Anaipalayam	8	8.5	0.3	0.3	Scl	Ca	24.5	14.8	0.7
		Anaikattipalayam	8.4	8.4	0.2	0.2	Scl	Ca	30	14.8	0.9
4.	Palampatty	Puthur Agraharam	7.8	8	0.9	1	Sl	Nc	33.9	4.5	0.68
5.	Veerapandi	Puthur Agraharam	8	8.1	1	0.6	Scl	Nc	33.9	4.5	0.68
		PM palayam	7.9	8.1	0.6	0.6	Sc	Ca	28.2	14.5	0.3
		Anaikattipalayam	8.3	8.3	0.6	0.7	Scl	Ca	30	14.8	0.9
		PM palayam	8.3	8.1	0.4	0.5	Scl	Nc	28.2	14.5	0.3
		Malayampatti	8	8	0.9	0.9	Scl	Nc	25.3	12.3	0.7
		Pattanam	8	8.1	0.9	0.8	Cl	Ca	37.3	8	1.3
6.	Akkaraipalayam	Keerapampadi	8.3	8.3	0.2	0.3	Sl	Nc	15.7	8.3	0.63
		Malayampatti	8.6	8.6	0.1	0.1	Sl	Nc	25.3	12.3	0.74
		Ilampillai	8.5	8.5	0.2	0.2	Scl	Ca	20.3	13.8	0.99
7.	Chennagiri	Veerapandi	7.9	8.2	0.7	0.4	Scl	Ca	24.6	18.6	0.4
		Pattanam	7.8	7.9	0.6	0.5	Sc	Ca	37.3	8	1.3
		PM palayam	8.2	8.1	0.2	0.3	Scl	Ca	28.2	14.5	0.3
8.	Putthur Agraharam	Pattanam	8.3	8.2	0.1	0.3	Scl	Ca	37.3	8	1.3
9.	Sittaneri	Pattanam	7.3	8	0.2	0.8	Sc	Ca	37.3	8	1.3
		Kurakkapuram	8	7.9	0.3	0.3	Scl	Ca	25.3	16.6	0.6
10.	Agraharapulaveri	Agraharapulaveri	8.3	8.3	0.4	0.4	Sc	Ca	37.4	14.4	0.24
		Pillanallur	8.4	8.3	0.3	0.3	Sc	Ca	19.3	16.8	0.85
		Anaikattipalayam	8.2	8.4	0.4	0.4	Sc	Ca	30	14.8	0.9
		Perumampatti	8.3	8.5	0.4	0.4	Scl	Ca	38.5	7.6	0.26
		Pudurmalayampatti	8.2	8.2	0.5	0.5	Sl	Nc	29.3	12.6	0.49
11.	Bairoji Agraharam	Anaikattipalayam	8.2	8.1	0.6	0.6	Scl	Ca	30	14.8	0.9
		Muthukalipatty	7.6	7.8	0.6	0.8	Sl	Nc	22.8	11.4	0.24
		Pudurmalayampatti	8.1	7.8	0.7	0.5	Sl	Nc	29.3	12.6	0.49
		Puthur Agraharam	7.7	7.9	0.4	1.3	Scl	Nc	33.9	4.5	0.68
12.	Uthamasolapuram	PM palayam	8.2	8.2	1	1	Sl	Ca	28.2	14.5	0.3
		Veerapandi	8.2	8.2	0.1	0.2	Scl	Ca	24.6	18.6	0.4
13.	Attavanaipulaveri	Ayipalayam	7.2	7	0.3	0.3	Scl	Nc	24	18.6	0.35

(pH) and soluble salts content (EC).

Morphological characters have been found altered, as soil profile features for the same soil series differ from polluted area to non-polluted area substantially. Adverse effects like discoloration, structural disturbances, upset in permeability, changes in pH and EC etc. are apparent in the soil profiles of polluted area than that of non-polluted area.

Besides, the current investigation emanating from the results of analysis of soil samples collected from sample sites, both surface and subsurface, also confirms the impact of pollution and consequently the presence of alkalinity is noted in 43 per cent of the surface samples and 48 per cent of the subsurface samples tested. The soil quality status of the samples analyzed in the basin and consequently the area affected indicate the following features (Table 2).

Table 2. Available nutrients status of Thirumanimutharu river basin of Salem district of Veerapandi block

Sr. no.	Village name	Soil series	N-S	N-SS	P-S	P-SS	K-S	K-SS	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe
1.	Muttanampalayam	Perumampatti	68	75	3.5	2	49	30	0.8	1.6	12.4	5.1
2.	Velanatham	Kurakkapuram	154	104	28	27	130	133	1.1	2.9	25.5	2.5
3.	Papparapatty	Anaipalayam	129	81	17	18	193	155	1.3	3.3	11.4	8.2
		Anaikattipalayam	91	123	18	33	113	98	1.4	4.4	9.6	17
4.	Palampatty	Puthur Agraharam	104	64	40	35	120	140	0.8	3.6	20	7.9
5.	Veerapandi	Puthur Agraharam	286	192	13	9	5	5	1.7	2.8	30	7.4
		PM palayam	180	133	17	15	55	48	1.2	3.5	35.5	8.8
		Anaikattipalayam	289	185	8	11	103	38	2.2	3.5	29.8	14
		PM palayam	238	225	6	6	5	15	1.4	3	35.6	8.9
		Malayampatti	185	140	7	9	18	15	1.4	3.5	34.8	17
6.	Akaraipalayam	Pattanam	285	188	28	17	91	168	2.6	2.9	21	12
		Keerapappampadi	112	89	21	22	40	53	0.8	1.9	11.4	9.5
		Malayampatti	85	87	11	10	10	35	1.1	1.3	7.2	3.9
7.	Chennagiri	Ilampillai	124	92	21	19	86	71	1.3	2.1	10.7	4.5
		Veerapandi	55	67	2	30	30	90	0.7	2	6.3	10
		Pattanam	68	56	9	7	74	72	1.9	3.4	14.9	11
8.	Putthur Agraharam	PM palayam	80	74	1.3	1.3	42	29	3.3	1.1	6.1	1.4
		Pattanam	102	69	2.2	1.2	95	106	5.6	10	9.3	3.8
9.	Sittaneri	Pattanam	92	87	18	21	65	105	1.9	2.7	15.6	6.2
		Kurakkapuram	85.3	91.3	27.3	39	77	103	1.0	1.3	9.1	4
10.	Agraharapulaveri	Agraharapulaveri	72	75	5	6	134	120	2.4	2.4	17.9	3.4
		Pillanallur	72	54	2	3	118	88	1.3	2.9	18.3	2.2
		Anaikattipalayam	72	97	7	11	191	166	1.5	4.1	28.3	6.5
		Perumampatti	32	102	6	8	145	95	1.2	3	28	3.5
		Pudurmalayampatti	47	82	7	4	150	87	0.9	2.5	28.5	7.3
11.	Bairoji Agraharam	Anaikattipalayam	172	196	6.3	8.3	80	89	1.4	3.7	25.2	18
		Muthukalipatty	87	43	3	4	89	150	1.1	2.5	18.6	22
		Pudurmalayampatti	96	63	3	2	87	50	1.3	1.6	17.2	4.8
		Puthur Agraharam	120	102	5	6	35	45	1	2.9	2	17
12.	Uttamasolapuram	PM palayam	110	117	5.5	4	101	97	1.4	3.1	13.3	7.7
		Veerapandi	112	102	6	3	115	63	1.3	2	11.5	7.9
13.	Attavanaipulaveri	Ayipalayam	176	151	15	18	212	199	1.1	1.8	23	5.1

Conclusion

The accumulation of soluble salts (EC) soils is quite normal. Accounting for 96 per cent of the area, since the physical condition of the most soil series favours the natural way of leaching out the salts. Salt accumulation is rather critical for germination and sensitive crops in only 3 per cent of the area, which warrant leaching measures to flush out salts. However, a marginal area of 1 per cent is at injurious level for most crops, which require adequate measures for their reclamation. The occurrence of saline alkaline lands is quite negligible.

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References

1. M. L. Jackson, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1973.
2. A. Walkley and C. A. Black, *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1934, **25**, 598.
3. W. L. Lindsay and W. A. Norwell, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1978, **42**, 421.
4. L. Sankararaaj, T. P. Subramanian, A. Siddhamalai and Farooque Ahmed, "Quality of Soil and Water for Agriculture in Noyyal River Basin, Tamilnadu", Special Report-98, SS & LUO, Coimbatore, 2002.